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From Knowledge to Habit: Assessing the Impact of Structured Instructional Intervention on Waste Literacy in Public School Pupils

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effectiveness of an integrated teaching approach in improving the awareness and practices of Grade 4 and Grade 5 public elementary pupils on proper solid waste management. Grounded in Bandura's Social Learning Theory, the intervention combined lecture discussions, video modeling, demonstrations, and hands-on activities that emphasized waste classification, the effects of improper disposal, and proper waste-handling behaviors aligned with the 3Rs and the CLAYGO policy. A total of 148 pupils from a public elementary school in Iloilo City participated in the study using a pre-experimental one-group pretest-posttest design. A researcher-made 60 item questionnaire, validated by experts and tested for reliability, was used to measure pupils' awareness of waste types, awareness of the effects of improper waste disposal, and actual waste management practices.

Results revealed a significant improvement in pupils' awareness of the types of solid waste after the intervention, indicating that the integrated teaching approach enhanced their ability to classify biodegradable and non-biodegradable materials. Although gains in awareness of the effects of improper waste disposal were modest, a significant increase was still observed among Grade 4 pupils. Moreover, pupils demonstrated high levels of solid waste management practices both before and after the intervention, with posttest scores showing increased consistency and frequency of proper waste-handling behavior. The Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test confirmed significant differences in most measured domains, affirming the intervention's positive impact.

The findings highlight the value of structured, engaging, and model-based environmental instruction in shaping young learners' knowledge and behavior toward sustainable waste practices. The study recommends integrating similar approaches across elementary levels to strengthen environmental responsibility and support school and community waste management initiatives.

Keywords: Environmental literacy, Solid waste classification, Biodegradable and Non-Biodegradable, CLAYGO policy, Public elementary learners

1. INTRODUCTION

Solid waste refers to any solid materials, including some liquids, that come from human activities, which are disposed of as being spent, useless, worthless, or in excess (Agardy et al., 2009). Over time, waste disposal has become a significant environmental problem, contributing to pollution, health hazards, and the depletion of our natural resources. Plastic waste in the surroundings is a major concern to all life forms. Plastic is produced and accumulated in the natural environment rapidly due to its uncritical use, insufficient recycling, and deposits in landfills. In 2019, the world's production of plastic reach 370 million tons, with just 9% being recycle, 12% being burned, and the some of it in the landfill or environments (Kumar et al., 2021). Agardy et al., (2009) found that municipal solid waste, as non-hazardous waste like paper and plastic produce in homes, businesses, and institutions and as mentioned in the 2024 United Nations environment program, is estimated to increase from 2.1 billion tonnes in 2023 to 3.8 billion tonnes in 2050. Despite people being aware of the risk of mismanaging solid waste, people still lack environmental knowledge, and their attitude often leads to poor waste disposal practices at home that can be observed by their siblings (Barloa et al., 2016).

Solid waste management includes collecting, sorting, storing and transporting solid waste for recycling, treating, and disposing (Agardy et al., 2009). An effective solid waste management is essential in reducing negative effects brought by globalization and urbanization in municipal or rural areas such as the Philippines (Hoang & Fogarassy, 2020), and the simplest way to observe this is by abiding with RA 9003 or Ecological Solid Waste Management Act. The legislation establishes solid waste management program to oversee the appropriate handling of solid waste, which involves solid waste management, treatment, proper segregation, collection, transport, storage, and treatment. Collaboration with various public education programs on waste management, waste reduction, and recycling enhances the program's effectiveness.

Furthermore, school is a medium that relay information and knowledge about solid waste management thus, as mandated by the government through Department of Education (DepEd) along with Commission on Higher Education (CHED) and several government agencies, carry out programs that seeks to strengthen education and information campaign against improper solid waste management (Section 55 of RA No. 9003). This section of the RA 9003 aims to develop the public's awareness regarding the ill effects of inappropriate solid waste management and possible community-based solutions. It also highlights the possible activities that are feasible and which have great impact on solid waste management in the country, such as conservation, resource recovery, recycling, source segregation, reuse, reduction, and composting. Lastly, it encourages the public, alongside organizations and NGOs, to publicly educate and patronize environmentally acceptable products, materials, or packaging.

Public schools in the Philippines are lacking in the practice of proper waste disposal, whether in the canteens or around the whole school campus, yet the school itself does not have any concrete policies, rules, and guidelines that minimize the school's production of solid waste (Nabor Jr. & Ortega-DelaCruz, 2020). It is a problem in global, national, and local levels since poor of solid waste management can contribute to flooding resulting in water contaminations that may cause shortages, adverse ill effects, and reconstruction and maintenance that may be too much for the municipality to handle (Koop & van Leeuwen, 2017). Inappropriate disposal of solid waste can result to environmental contamination and unhygienic conditions. It can cause Vector-borne disease outbreaks. The prosperity, health, and environment can all be negatively impacted by improper sorting of waste. Poor solid waste management pollutes the oceans, clog sewers, and causes flooding (Ijjasz-Vasquez et al., 2018).

The pupils in the public elementary school, aged 6 to 12, are at a critical stage in which they practice and shape their behavior and attitudes. It is important to teach them at this stage responsibility to clean their area after they eat and use it and proper segregation of their waste. Refusing the waste may risk the health of the pupils. Another effect of inefficient waste disposal is the pollution of underground water sources that may cause landslides, flooding, and air pollution. Initiatives aiming to engage the community to be involved in waste management should start from an early age since molding human behavior instantaneously is a challenging task (Sulistiyawati et al., 2020).

Catan and Molina (2020) on basic education students' knowledge of solid waste management shows that they have a solid grasp of key concepts, including the definition of the solid waste, consequences of inappropriate disposal, forbidden activities, waste management programs in school, the importance of waste management, and their own responsibilities. However, their understanding of related laws is limited. Similarly, Madrigal and Reyes (2020) found that students are generally aware of waste management issues, but only at the secondary and tertiary levels. In contrast, Nabor and Ortega (2022) reported low levels of awareness among elementary students in terms of behaviors, understanding, and practices related to the management of solid waste. The results also suggest that, despite the school's efforts to implement waste management practices, students still need clear and structured objectives to emphasize the significance of waste management.

Studying the types of solid waste, their effects on improper waste disposal, and the practice of proper waste disposal helps protect the environment and health. It prepares young learners to take action to solve waste problems. Awareness of proper waste disposal can help reduce the negative ecological and human health impacts, supporting economic growth and enhancing the quality of life, and is essential for lessening the waste management issues that harm people's health and the environment (Biol et al., 2021). Encouraging responsible and sustainable waste-handling behaviors from a young age is important.

On the other hand, ineffective waste management and improper disposal of waste matter can contribute to the emergence of various diseases, infections, and infestations (Sultana et al., 2021). This encompasses a range of illnesses associated with solid waste, including malaria, diarrhoea, dysentery, cholera, typhoid, and worm diseases (Sultana et al., 2021). Furthermore, inadequate waste disposal can generate an environment conducive to the proliferation of pathogenic microorganisms and disease vectors, as well as provoke public disturbances due to unsightliness and unpleasant odors. It may lead to the contaminants of the soil, surface water and ground water, and it can also lead to physical risks, fire hazards, and poisoning from insecticides and pesticides (OL Create, n.d.).

1.1 Theoretical Framework of the Study

This study is based on the Social Learning Theory of Albert Bandura, especially observational learning and the use of a model. Social Learning Theory serves as a "bridge" between behaviorism and cognitive theory by emphasizing the role of cognitive processes in learning (McLeod, 2025). According to Bandura (1997) as cited by McLeod (2025), individuals actively process information, and their behavior is shaped by the consequences of their actions. People acquire new behaviors by observing and imitating models, which leads to the development of knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs based on those observed consequences.

Mayer (2009) suggest that video modeling can result in faster skill acquisition and better generalization than in-person modeling. Also noted that screen-based media effectively capture and sustain students' attention because of its engaging nature. Lackman et al., (2021) add that video modeling allows educators to highlight specific stimulus characteristics while minimizing distractions. Chen and Wu (2015) further argue that pairing video modeling with instructional prompts and positive reinforcement such as verbal praise or tangible rewards is more effective than video modeling alone. This combination promotes better learning, retention, and generalization of target skills.

The researcher used educational tools like videos about the types of solid waste, the effects of improper waste disposal, and practices on how to dispose the solid waste properly and how to reduce, reuse, and recycle waste during the intervention. The topic on solid waste was presented and was followed by a short video about waste management and other videos related to solid waste disposal. After watching the video, the pupils were asked what the

video was all about and what actions were needed to solve the problem of waste disposal. Through watching videos, the pupils can imitate and apply the behavior to themselves.

In the context of this study, elementary pupils learned proper waste practices through observation, guided instruction, and modelled demonstrations. The intervention utilized in this study included video presentations, lecture discussions, and interactive activities, which served as modelling tools for pupils. These tools represented structured forms of observational learning, helping the learners to imitate proper behavior such as classifying biodegradable and non-biodegradable waste, practicing the 3Rs (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle), and identifying the effects of improper waste management.

Bandura's theory supports the idea that when children observe responsible waste practices being modeled in an engaging and consistent manner, they are more likely to adopt those behaviors themselves. This aligns with the goal of the research, which was to influence pupils' awareness and actions toward proper waste disposal through modeled educational interventions.

Measuring the pupil's awareness of solid waste and its effect to the immediate community and teaching them the possible and correct practices and allowing them to see the essence of proper waste disposal allowed the pupils to practice proper waste management and helped them develop this new skill for the benefit of their immediate community. Ultimately, the goal of this research methodology would have been to demonstrate the effectiveness of teaching integrated approaches such as teaching through lecture video, employing 3Rs, and letting them experience the process to shape their behaviour towards proper waste disposal.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research Design

This study employed quantitative research, utilizing the process of collecting numerical data to test the relationship between the two variables and the hypothesis. This study used pre-experimental research to determine if a specific intervention influenced the outcome (Creswell & Creswell, 2023). Specifically, this study used a pre-experimental research design, a single section from Grade 4 and Grade 5 underwent a pre-test to measure their existing knowledge of awareness, practices, and behavior towards waste disposal. The intervention, the integrated teaching approach using a series of lecture video presentations, lecture about 3Rs, and CLAYGO policy was implemented after the pre-test. Lastly, the post-test was conducted to see if there were changes in the result after the intervention.

This design allowed the researcher to determine the effectiveness of the integrated teaching approach to the pupils' knowledge and attitudes regarding waste disposal before and after the intervention.

2.2 Participants of the Study

The participants of this study were Grade 4 and Grade 5 pupils from a public elementary school in Iloilo City. A total of 148 pupils (76 from Grade 4 and 72 from Grade 5), consisting of both male and female learners aged 9 to 12 years old, were involved in the study. The participants were selected through purposive sampling in coordination with the school principal, who identified three sections from Grade 4 and Grade 5.

The participation of the pupils depended on the consent of the principal, teachers, and parents since the pupils were all minors. The chosen sections of Grade 4 and 5 pupils were both heterogeneous and included male and female pupils. The excluded pupils are those without parent's consent, those enrolled in a private school and were not in either Grade 4 or Grade 5. Ethical considerations were observed, as pupils' decision to engage in the survey depended on their availability, willingness, and especially permission of their parents to allow them to participate. The pupils were allowed to decline participation without penalty.

2.3 Research Instrument

The study employed a researcher-made questionnaire checklist, which was divided into two sections. Part I collected the respondents' profiles, such as their names and grade levels, while Part II measured three components, namely: Part A, the awareness on types of solid waste; Part B, awareness on the effects of solid waste; and Part C, proper waste disposal practices. Part A consisted of 20 items to assess pupils' awareness of the type of waste in which they identified the solid waste as either biodegradable or non-biodegradable and gained 1 point for every correct answer and 0 if incorrect. Part B consisted of 20 items to measure awareness of the effects of improper waste disposal and was scored 1 for a correct answer and 0 for each wrong answer. Part C consisted of 20 items to assess practices related to proper waste disposal which was scored as follows: 1 for Never (Wala), 2 for Sometimes (Kon Kisa), and 3 for Always (Pirmi).

The validity of the questionnaire was assessed by the three experts in the field of science with either master's or doctoral degrees in science teaching and research. These experts provided evaluations, critiques, and suggestions that the researchers considered and integrated to enhance the instrument's quality, validity, and relevance. After revisions, the instrument was approved by the panel of experts for content validation.

2.4 Data Gathering Procedure and Analysis

This study utilized a researcher-made instrument and was conducted at a selected elementary school during the school year 2024-2025. An official letter and request were sent to the principal of the said school to seek approval to conduct the study. Upon receiving the approval from the school's principal, the study commenced. Data collection was carried out in three phases:

2.4.1 Preparation and Pretest Phase

During the pretest phase, the researchers approached the school heads to utilize a single group of Grade 4 and 5 pupils for the study. Pupils in this group had signed consent forms from both parents and themselves, ensuring that all ethical considerations were addressed. This group met with the researchers according to the researchers' available schedules, while also considering the pupils' class schedules within a specific time-frame. Once all requirements and ethical considerations had been satisfied, the study commenced by administering questionnaires to assess the pupils' awareness and knowledge of proper waste management. The data collected maintained the anonymity and confidentiality of the pupils' responses.

Furthermore, at this phase, all materials and instruments needed for the study, such as research instruments, lesson plans, lecture videos, trash bins with labels and color coded based on DepEd guidelines, and other instructional resources required for classroom teaching, were prepared in this phase.

2.4.2 Intervention Phase

In this phase, the interventions took place, based on the modified lesson plan prepared by the researchers. Lesson plan comparisons with lecture videos and interventions were prepared, as well as other materials such as signages, labels, and color-coded trash bins.

2.4.3 Posttest Phase

Following the exposure of the pupils to the interventions prepared by the researchers, the researchers conducted a post-test using the same instrument used in the pre-test. This was to identify whether there were significant changes in their practices towards proper waste management. After gathering the necessary data, an analysis was performed, and researchers ensured to securely store all relevant documents, safeguarding the confidentiality of the respondents' backgrounds and upholding their right to privacy.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Level of Awareness of Types of Solid Waste Before and After the Integrated Teaching Approach

In the pretest for Grade 4 pupils, 59.74% scored average level of awareness, while 16.88% have high level, and the rest have poor level of awareness. The mean score was 13.53, indicating that, on average, learners demonstrated a basic to moderate understanding of the types of solid waste prior to the intervention. The standard deviation of 3.05 reflected a moderate spread in the distribution of scores, suggesting that some pupils scored considerably higher or lower than the group average. This variability indicates that while some pupils had a fair grasp of the topic, others may have lacked foundational knowledge or exhibited misconceptions.

After the intervention, 38.16% of pupils reached high level of awareness. The mean score increased to 15.89. The reduction in standard deviation to 2.64 implies that pupils' scores became more tightly clustered around the mean, suggesting greater consistency in understanding across the group. This narrowing range could indicate that the learning experience was more uniformly grasped. In the pretest for Grade 5 pupils, 68.06% scored within the average range, while 18.06% have high level of awareness. The mean score of 13.89 suggests that most pupils held a moderate level of prior knowledge about solid waste types. The standard deviation of 3.12 again points to moderate variability, indicating a mix of levels of understanding within the class, where some pupils may have had difficulty differentiating between biodegradable and non-biodegradable materials.

Following the intervention, the percentage of pupils who have high awareness rose to 47.22%. The mean score increased to 16.11. The standard deviation slightly decreased to 2.68, reflecting a marginally more uniform level of performance among learners.

These results align with previous research that attributes knowledge gaps in environmental awareness to limited structured instruction. Sarona and Sotto (2020) emphasized the need for integrated ecological education at the elementary level. Taypin et.al. (2024) discussed how formal instruction contributes to baseline environmental understanding, while Herrera (2018) noted that in the absence of targeted strategies, pupils may develop misconceptions about ecological issues.

The post-intervention changes in scores are supported by Bantang (2022), who highlighted that real-life examples and visual aids contribute to stronger conceptual learning. Sarona and Sotto (2020) also underscored the role of interactive and contextualized strategies in improving content retention. Aguilar (2021) added that multisensory learning enhances engagement and understanding, especially in science education.

Table 1. The awareness on types of solid waste as shown by the learners scores before and after the implementation of the integrated teaching approach. Legend: Poor (Below 10), Average (11- 16), High (17 - 20).

	Before Intervention		After Intervention		
	f	%	f	%	
Grade 4	Poor	14	18.42	1	1.32
	Average	50	65.79	46	60.53
	High	12	15.79	29	38.16
	Total	76		76	
Mean	13.53		15.89		
SD	3.05		2.64		
Grade 5		f	%	f	%
	Poor	11	15.28	2	2.78
	Average	49	68.06	36	50.00
	High	13	18.06	34	47.22
	Total	72		72	
	Mean	13.53		16.11	
	SD	3.05		2.68	

3.2 Level of Awareness of Effects of the Solid Waste Before and After the Integrated Teaching Approach

The pretest for Grade 4 showed that 70.13% of the pupils have poor level of awareness of the effects of solid waste, while only 6.85% scored high. The mean score was 8.58, that implies a generally low level of understanding in recognizing how improper waste disposal affects environmental aspects such as air, water, and soil. The standard deviation was 3.76, indicating a wide distribution of scores. This spread suggests that while a few pupils may have demonstrated partial understanding, most showed significant gaps, and the level of awareness across the group was highly inconsistent.

After the intervention, the mean score increased to 9.97, with a standard deviation of 4.11. A notable percentage of pupils (42.11%) increased in awareness to average level, while 52.63% remained under the poor level of awareness. The rise in mean suggests a slight gain in group performance, however, the increase in standard deviation implies that score variability also grew, meaning that while some pupils improved, others may not have benefitted equally. The posttest data suggests that the class continued to exhibit diverse levels of understanding, and the learning outcomes were not uniformly distributed. The Grade 5 pretest results reveal that 67.12% of the pupils also have poor level of awareness and only 6.85% reached the high level. The mean score was 9.23, slightly higher than that of Grade 4, which still reflected a low general level of awareness. The standard deviation was 3.81, which, like in Grade 4, suggested a wide variation in responses indicating unequal levels of environmental knowledge among pupils.

In the posttest, the mean score increased slightly to 9.45, with a standard deviation of 3.86. A majority (66.67%) of the pupils still belonged to the poor level of awareness, and only 4.17% reached the high level of awareness. The minimal change in the mean, combined with a high standard deviation, suggests that learners' awareness remained limited and that the group as a whole did not move toward a more uniform or deeper understanding of the environmental effects of improper waste disposal. These findings suggest that even after instructional intervention, pupils particularly in Grade 5 struggled to fully grasp the abstract ideas of the consequences of improper waste management. The consistently high standard deviations in both grade levels and test stages indicate persistent variability in learners' comprehension. While some pupils showed improvement, others continued to have difficulty internalizing the environmental impacts being taught.

This outcome aligns with Francisco's (2020) study that noted that elementary pupils often face challenges in understanding abstract environmental concepts unless these are contextualized through direct, real-life experiences. Similarly, Tabamo (2021) emphasized that without repeated exposure and strong contextual links, pupils are less likely to recognize the long-term effects of their actions on nature. Salvador and Perez (2021) also argued that students are unlikely to grasp the real impact of pollution unless they personally witness or vividly imagine its effects.

The posttest data also reflected the suggestion by Tabamo (2021) that abstract content, particularly among older learners, may require more immersive, experience-based approaches, such as simulations, case studies, or hands-on environmental tasks. Francisco (2020) further emphasized that emotional connection and real-world relevance are essential for deeper cognitive engagement, especially in topics like ecological cause-and-effect. These findings

imply that while integrated teaching may have supported knowledge in basic classification and practices, additional strategies such as reflective discussion, role-playing, or community-based projects may be needed to help pupils make stronger cognitive and emotional connections to the consequences of poor environmental behavior.

Table 2. The awareness on the effects of solid waste among grade 4 and 5 learners before and after the intervention.

Legend: Poor (Below 10), Average (11- 16), High (17 - 20).

	Before Intervention		After Intervention		
	f	%	f	%	
Grade 4	Poor	54	71.05	40	52.63
	Average	17	22.37	32	42.11
	High	5	6.58	4	5.26
	Total	76		76	
	Mean	8.58		9.97	
	SD	3.76		4.11	
Grade 5		f	%	f	%
	Poor	48	66.67	48	66.67
	Average	19	26.39	21	29.17
	High	5	6.94	3	4.17
	Total	72		72	
		Mean	8.58		9.45
	SD	3.76		3.86	

3.3 Level of Performance in Practices in Handling Solid Waste Before and After the Integrated Teaching Approach

To evaluate pupils' actual practices in managing solid waste, a 20-item checklist with 60 item total points was administered before and after the intervention. The Grade 4 pretest results reveal that 74.03% of the pupils showed high level of performance in terms of their practices in handling solid waste, while 25.97% have average level of performance. No pupils were identified in the poor category. The mean score was 44.75, indicating that learners engage in proper solid waste management practices with relative consistency. The standard deviation was 5.92, suggesting that while most pupils responded similarly, there was still a moderate spread in their levels of practice.

In the posttest, 89.47% of the pupils have high level of performance, and only a small percentage (10.53%) remained in the average category. The mean score increased to 47.84, and the standard deviation decreased to 5.64, indicating not only higher levels of reported practice but also greater consistency across the class. The lower standard deviation suggests a narrowing gap between learners, with more pupils aligning closely in their frequency and application of correct waste management habits.

In the Grade 5 pretest, 83.56% of the pupils have already high level of performance, and the remaining 16.44% have average level. The mean score was 44.90, which reflects a strong overall baseline in solid waste management behavior among the learners. The standard deviation was 6.07, showing a moderate amount of variation among pupils' self-reported practices, possibly due to variations in personal initiative, home reinforcement, or attentiveness to school rules.

In the posttest, 86.11% of pupils reached the high category. The mean score increased to 47.27, while the standard deviation decreased slightly to 5.82. This decrease in variability implies that pupils' behavior became more aligned and consistent, suggesting that a larger portion of the class engaged in solid waste management practices with regularity and confidence.

The strong pretest results in both grade levels can be attributed to institutional and routine-based environmental programs already present in school environments. This is consistent with Sarona and Sotto's findings (2020) that programs such as CLAYGO (Clean As You Go) and regular classroom maintenance tasks play a significant role in instilling proper waste management habits among young learners. Similarly, Taypin (2024) emphasized the influence of school-wide norms and teacher-led modeling on students' environmental behavior, while Herrera (2018) noted that consistent behavioral routines in early education create lasting impressions that extend into daily life.

The posttest findings reinforce insights from Moreno (2021), who highlighted that structured reinforcement and consistent modeling are essential for maintaining and enhancing pro-environmental behaviors in learners. Salvador and Perez (2021) supported the idea that hands-on and experience-based strategies are more effective than theoretical approaches in influencing behavior. Additionally, Aguilar (2021) stressed the power of repetition and visual cues, especially when these are supported by school and community engagement, to improve retention and execution of environmental actions.

Together, these findings suggest that while pupils may already practice waste management due to existing environmental efforts, structured instruction can still contribute meaningfully to deepening these habits, increasing behavioral consistency, and strengthening pupils' confidence in applying their learning in real-life contexts.

Table 3. The performance in solid waste management practices among grade 4 and 5 learners before and after the intervention.

Legend: Poor (Below 20), Average (21-40), High (41 - 60).

	Before Intervention		After Intervention		
	f	%	f	%	
Grade 4	Poor	0	0.00	0	0.00
	Average	20	26.32	8	10.53
	High	56	73.68	68	89.47
	Total	76		76	
Mean	44.75		47.84		
SD	5.92		5.64		
Grade 5		f	%	f	%
	Poor	0	0.00	0	0.00
	Average	12	16.67	10	13.89
	High	60	83.33	62	86.11
	Total	72		72	
	Mean	44.90		47.27	
SD	6.07		5.82		

3.4 Difference in the Levels of Awareness in Types of Solid Waste Before and After the Integrated Teaching Approach

Grade 4 pupils' mean score increased from 13.53 to 15.89, resulting in a mean gain of 2.36. The Wilcoxon test produced a z-value of -4.663 and a p-value of .000, indicating a statistical difference in awareness. This result showed that the integrated teaching strategy was highly effective in enhancing the Grade 4 pupils' ability to correctly classify solid waste as either biodegradable or non-biodegradable.

Grade 5 pupils' mean score also improved from 13.89 to 16.11, with a mean gain of 2.22. The Wilcoxon test yielded a z-value of -4.116 and a p-value of .000, which, similarly with Grade 4 pupils, indicated a difference in the pupils' awareness levels.

The consistent results for both grade levels suggested that the teaching intervention, which combined visual materials, interactive activities, and contextual instruction, helped learners better understand how to categorize different types of waste. This outcome supports the findings of Bantang (2022), who noted that visual and contextualized instruction enhanced learners' ability to retain and apply classification-based knowledge. Furthermore, Sarona and Sotto (2020) observed that learners benefited most from environmental topics when they were taught using real-world examples and group-based activities that allowed them to explore and analyze materials firsthand.

This statistical evidence confirmed that the integrated teaching approach had a statistical and educational meaningful impact on pupils' awareness of the types of solid waste. This improvement reinforced the value of differentiated, visually rich, and experience-based environmental instruction in promoting foundational understanding among elementary learners.

Table 4. The results of the Wilcoxon Signed-Ranks Test for Grade 4 and Grade 5 learners' pretest and posttest awareness of the types of solid waste.

<i>Awareness of Types of Solid Waste</i>						
		N	Mean	Diff.	z-value	p= value
Grade 4	Before	76	13.53			
	After	76	15.89	2.36	-4.663	.000
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		N	Mean	Diff.	z-value	p= value
Grade 5	Before	72	13.89			
	After	72	16.11	2.22	-4.116	.000

*Significant at 0.05

3.5 Difference in the Level of Awareness in the Effects of Solid Waste Before and After the Integrated Teaching Approach

Grade 4 pupils' mean score increased from 8.58 to 9.97, resulting in a mean gain of 1.39. The Wilcoxon test produced a z-value of -2.838 and a p-value of .008, indicating a statistical difference in awareness of waste effects. In contrast, Grade 5 pupils recorded a mean gain of only 0.23, with pretest and posttest scores rising from 9.23 to 9.46, respectively. The Wilcoxon test yielded a z-value of -0.187 and a p-value of .852, which indicated that there is no difference. This showed that the instructional strategy did not produce a measurable effect on Grade 5 pupils' awareness of environmental consequences.

The results revealed a critical difference between grade levels: while Grade 4 pupils benefited from the intervention and showed improvement, Grade 5 pupils did not exhibit the same level of conceptual growth. This contrast suggested that younger learners were more responsive to visual and structured lessons, while older pupils might have required more complex, reflective, or emotionally engaging strategies to fully grasp abstract cause-and-effect relationships in environmental science. This finding aligned with Tabamo (2021), who emphasized that older elementary pupils may have needed higher-order thinking activities, such as simulations or project-based tasks, to process environmental effects meaningfully. Francisco (2020) similarly stated that pupils tended to retain more when environmental content is emotionally and contextually connected to their daily lives. Additionally, Salvador and Perez (2021) observed that without direct experience or concrete illustrations, learners often failed to internalize the impact of human actions on ecological systems.

These results suggested that the teaching strategy was partially effective in raising awareness of the environmental effects of solid waste. Its success with Grade 4 pupils supported the effectiveness of visual and activity-based learning in younger learners, while the lack of progress among Grade 5 pupils highlighted the need for more adaptive and engaging strategies to bridge gaps in understanding complex ecological consequences.

Table 5. Comparison between pretest and posttest scores of Grades 4 and 5 learners on their awareness of the effects of improper solid waste disposal.

<i>Awareness of Effects of Solid Waste</i>						
		N	Mean	Diff.	z-value	p= value
Grade 4	Before	76	8.58			
	After	76	9.97	1.39	-2.838	.008
<hr/>						
		N	Mean	Diff.	z-value	p= value
Grade 5	Before	72	9.23			
	After	72	9.46	0.23	-0.187	.852

*Significant at 0.05

3.6 Difference in the Performance Level in Practices on Handling Solid Waste Before and After the Integrated Approach

To assess the effectiveness of the integrated teaching approach in improving pupils' actual solid waste management practices, the Wilcoxon Signed-Ranks Test was applied to compare pretest and posttest scores. The assessment was based on a 20-item checklist where pupils responded to various behavior-based scenarios such as segregation, recycling, and proper disposal by selecting how often they practiced each one: Never, Sometimes, or Always. Scores were calculated to evaluate behavioral consistency and responsibility in waste handling.

Grade 4 pupils' mean score increased from 44.75 to 47.84, resulting in a mean gain of 3.09. The Wilcoxon test generated a z-value of -3.483 and a p-value of .000, which indicated a statistical difference in waste management practices. This suggested that the integrated teaching strategy not only reinforced existing habits but also successfully helped more learners shift from average to high levels of practice. For Grade 5 pupils, a mean gain of 2.38 was recorded, with scores rising from 44.90 to 47.28. The Wilcoxon test showed a z-value of -2.839 and a p-value of .005, which also indicated a statistical difference, although the effect was slightly lower compared to Grade 4.

These results confirmed that the instructional intervention had a meaningful and statistical effect on enhancing pupils' actual behaviors related to waste disposal. The increase in both mean scores and the shift in performance levels supported the idea that environmental practices could be strengthened through deliberate instruction and reinforcement. The stronger gain among Grade 4 pupils may have reflected their higher receptiveness to structure, modeling, and repetition, while Grade 5 pupils also responded positively, though possibly influenced by already well-developed habits.

The findings affirmed the conclusion of Moreno (2021), who highlighted that consistent reinforcement of environmental routines leads to long-term behavioral improvement. Salvador and Perez (2021) also emphasized that hands-on and observable activities made abstract environmental principles more actionable. Moreover, Aguilar (2021) argued that the use of visual aids and step-by-step guidance promoted practical application and retention of pro-environmental behaviors. The gains in both grade levels, even from an already strong pretest baseline, suggested that structured interventions not only informed but also reinvigorated and deepened behavioral commitment to proper solid waste management among elementary pupils.

Table 6. The statistical analysis of Grade 4 and 5 learners pretest and posttest performance on proper waste disposal practices.

<i>Practices of Proper Waste Disposal</i>						
		N	Mean	Diff.	z-value	p=
Grade 4	Before	76	44.75			
	After	76	47.84	3.09	-3.483	.000
<hr/>						
		N	Mean	Diff.	z-value	p=
Grade 5	Before	72	44.90			
	After	72	47.28	2.38	-2.839	.005

*Significant at 0.05

4. FINDINGS AND CONCLUSIONS

4.1 Findings

The following findings were drawn from the results of this study.

- Awareness of solid waste types was limited prior to the intervention, with most Grade 4 and Grade 5 pupils performing at an average level. This indicates a gap in their ability to identify and classify types of waste accurately.
- Pupils' awareness of the effects of solid waste management was generally poor across both grade levels. Many pupils were unable to explain or understand the long-term consequences of improper waste management, particularly environmental and health-related outcomes.
- Solid waste practices were already strong in both grade levels before the intervention, suggesting the presence of existing environmental routines in school such as CLAYGO or classroom clean-up policies.
- After the implementation of the intervention, there was an improvement in pupils' awareness of the types of solid waste, showing that the teaching strategy was effective in enhancing conceptual understanding.

- Grade 4 pupils showed improvement in their awareness of the effects of solid waste, while Grade 5 pupils did not, indicating a potential developmental difference in processing abstract environmental concepts.
- Both Grade 4 and Grade 5 pupils demonstrated improvements in waste management practices, with more pupils moving into the high-performance level after the intervention.
- The most substantial improvements in both awareness and practice were observed among Grade 4 pupils, suggesting that younger learners may be more responsive to visual and interactive strategies.
- The teaching strategy was found to be most effective in enhancing concrete knowledge and observable behaviors, and less effective in fostering understanding of complex, cause-effect relationships among older learners.

4.2 Conclusions

In relation to the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

- The integrated teaching strategy was effective in improving awareness of solid waste types across both grade levels. Among Grade 4 pupils, the mean score increased from 13.53 to 15.89, while among Grade 5, it increased from 13.89 to 16.11. The Wilcoxon Signed-Ranks Test yielded p-values of .000 for both levels, confirming an improvement and validating the strategy's value in environmental instruction.
- Grade 4 pupils appeared to benefit more than Grade 5 pupils in both cognitive and behavioral domains. Their mean gain in awareness of solid waste types was 2.36, slightly higher than that of Grade 5's (2.22), possibly due to developmental readiness for structured and visually enriched learning experiences.
- The strategy had limited impact on abstract content, particularly understanding the long-term environmental consequences of improper waste disposal. Although there was a mean score increase among Grade 4 pupils from 8.58 to 9.97 and among Grade 5 from 9.23 to 9.45, both remained within the "poor" awareness level, suggesting the need for deeper, experience-based instructional strategies.
- The pupils' already high pretest performance in waste management practices was further enhanced. Grade 4 pupils' mean score improved from 44.75 to 47.84, and Grade 5 pupils' from 44.90 to 47.27, demonstrating that modeling, repetition, and reinforcement strategies effectively strengthened existing pro-environmental behaviors.
- Structured school initiatives, such as CLAYGO and 3Rs campaigns, likely provided a solid foundation for pupils, especially given that over 74% of Grade 4 and 83% of Grade 5 pupils already have "high" levels of practice even before the intervention.
- The results affirm prior research findings that contextualized, interactive, and visually supported instruction leads to measurable improvements in both environmental knowledge and behavioral outcomes, particularly in younger learners.
- Instruction that does not match the developmental level of learners such as expecting abstract reasoning from pupils who benefit more from concrete experiences may yield limited gains, especially in areas like understanding environmental consequences.
- Overall, the study confirms that integrated environmental instruction through lectures, video modeling, and practical demonstrations is a viable and effective approach to improving awareness and reinforcing solid waste management practices among elementary public school pupils.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are organized across three levels of implementation to guide teachers, school administrators, and future researchers respectively.

Immediate classroom actions teachers can implement directly in their lessons:

- Since both Grade 4 and Grade 5 pupils showed improvement in identifying types of solid waste, teachers are encouraged to adopt visually supported materials (e.g., labeled charts, posters, etc.) and structured observation tasks to reinforce classification skills between biodegradable and non-biodegradable waste during Science lessons.
- Given that pupils demonstrated limited improvement in awareness of the effects of improper waste disposal, particularly in abstract concepts, teachers should utilize simulations, localized storytelling, and project-based learning that make environmental consequences visible and relatable (e.g., "What happens when trash clogs a canal?").
- Instructional materials should be differentiated. Grade 4 pupils may benefit from guided practice and pictorial-based worksheets, while Grade 5 pupils can be challenged with cause-and-effect charts, case analysis, and reflective writing about community waste issues.
- Incorporate local environmental issues and real-life case studies into learning materials (e.g., Iloilo's landfill data, flooding due to blocked canals) to promote place-based learning.

School-level initiatives that require institutional coordination and policy support:

- To address the moderate understanding of environmental consequences, cross-curricular integration should be applied embedding topics on waste and sustainability into Araling Panlipunan (citizenship roles), ESP (values formation), and Science (pollution, ecosystems) subjects.
- Since many pupils already had high levels of practice, programs like CLAYGO and the 3Rs should be institutionalized in schools as part of daily routines, not just campaign-based, and monitored through classroom behavior checklists or weekly reflection logs.
- Since pupils' behavior at school was strong but their awareness of consequences was weak, schools should engage parents through take-home assignments, waste-segregation diaries, or home audits where children inspect and reflect on household waste habits.
- LGUs and Barangay Councils should support schools by donating color-coded bins, installing educational murals, or providing barangay data on waste problems that students can analyze in Science or Araling Panlipunan classes.
- Conduct quarterly school-wide clean-up drives tied to Science or EPP objectives to give pupils direct involvement in reducing school waste. Future study directions for researchers and academics:
- For Future Researchers, since the study showed gains in short-term knowledge, further studies may explore retention of learning through delayed posttests or interviews weeks after the intervention.
- Comparative studies may also investigate the effectiveness of game-based learning, mobile apps, or community immersion projects in teaching solid waste management to pupils in urban vs. rural settings.

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